

AUTOMATIC HYDROPONIC SYSTEM.

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Abstract - This paper presents a DIY hydroponic system that uses Arduino technology to combine pH and EC sensors. The system ensures a regulated environment for healthy plant growth in hydroponics, which requires regular monitoring of nutrient solution pH and EC values. Arduino microcontrollers automate the monitoring process, allowing real-time data collection and feedback control. The system includes sensors for pH and EC, plant growth parts, a fertilizer reservoir, and a water circulation system. The system's parameters are controlled, and sensor data is gathered by Arduino microcontrollers. The EC sensor evaluates the solution's total nutrient concentration, while the pH sensor monitors the nutrient solution's acidity or alkalinity. The data is processed and sent to an interface for remote monitoring and modifications. The system's effectiveness and efficiency were assessed through experiments, demonstrating its ability to maintain ideal pH and EC values for plant growth. This affordable and easily attainable DIY hydroponic system is a promising basis for further research and advancements in automated hydroponic farming techniques.

I. INTRODUCTION

An effective, automated, and controlled method of plant cultivation is provided by the hydroponic system's integration of pH and EC sensors with Arduino technology. The investigation presented in this paper lays the groundwork for future developments and uses of automated cultivation systems while also improving sustainability and productivity in hydroponics.

Plants grown hydroponically essentially don't need any soil. It is a more effective method of giving your plants food and water. Plants need the nutrients and water found in the soil, not the soil itself. The two main purposes of soil are to anchor plant roots and provide nutrients to the plants. Hydroponic gardeners can use a variety of inert media, such as clay pellets, river rock, coconut fiber, rock wool, or Styrofoam, to support their plants.

The phrase hydroponics comes from the Latin for "working water." Water fills the void left by the absence of soil by giving plant life nutrition, moisture, and oxygen. Under the meticulous hydroponic routine, plants thrive, ranging from orchids to watermelons and jalapeños. Hydroponic gardens, with their clever design, use 90% less water and less land than traditional agriculture to produce gorgeous fruits and flowers in half the time. I strongly advise reading the Fresh Water Systems article if you'd like to learn more about the hydroponics system.

Since every plant has individual nutrient needs, hydroponics makes measuring and adding the right amounts of fertilizers to the water solutions simpler. If you do it by hand, it can be rather tiresome. Since I'm not an expert in hydroponics, I have no idea how much fertilizer should be applied to the water solution. However, I can assist you in creating and building your hydroponic system, which will allow you to use solenoid valves, which can be adjusted by measured values, to precisely measure and add nutrients to the water.

This paper describes how to build your own Hydroponics system with an Arduino, an OLED display module, a TOF10120 laser

distance rangefinder, a pH sensor, an EC sensor or TDS meter, and a DS18B20 one-wire digital temperature sensor.

1. "Automated Hydroponics System using IoT: A Review". This paper discusses the integration of the Internet of Things (IoT) in hydroponic systems to automate various processes such as nutrient supply, pH monitoring, and environmental control. It provides insights into the benefits and challenges associated with implementing IoT in hydroponics.

2. "Advances in Automated Control Systems for Hydroponics: A Comprehensive Review". This review paper explores recent advancements in automated control systems for hydroponic setups. It covers topics such as sensor technologies, control algorithms, and integration with smart farming platforms. The paper also discusses the potential impact of these advancements on improving crop yields and resource efficiency.

3. "Hydroponic Systems Automation: A Survey of Technologies and Applications". This survey paper overviews various automation technologies used in hydroponic systems. It discusses different approaches for automating nutrient delivery, pH regulation, and environmental monitoring. The paper also highlights real-world applications of automated hydroponic systems in agriculture and horticulture.

4. "Integration of Machine Learning Techniques in Automatic Hydroponic Systems: A Review". This paper reviews the integration of machine learning techniques in automatic hydroponic systems. It examines how machine learning algorithms can optimize nutrient management, predict plant growth patterns, and enhance overall system efficiency. The review also discusses challenges and future research directions in this area.

5. "Sensing and Control Technologies for Automated Hydroponic Farming: A Literature Review". This literature review focuses on sensing and control technologies used in

automated hydroponic farming. It discusses various sensor types for monitoring parameters such as nutrient levels, pH, temperature, and humidity. Additionally, the paper examines control strategies for maintaining optimal growing conditions in hydroponic environments.

6. "Recent Advances in Robotics and Automation for Hydroponic Agriculture: A Review". This review paper discusses recent advances in robotics and automation technologies for hydroponic agriculture. It covers topics such as robotic harvesting systems, automated nutrient delivery systems, and autonomous crop monitoring. The paper also examines challenges and opportunities for integrating robotics into hydroponic farming practices.

7. "Smart Hydroponic Systems: A Comprehensive Review of Sensors and Control Strategies". This comprehensive review focuses on the integration of sensors and control strategies in smart hydroponic systems. It discusses various sensor technologies for monitoring plant health, nutrient levels, and environmental parameters. The paper also explores different control strategies for automating nutrient delivery and maintaining optimal growing conditions.

8. "Wireless Sensor Networks for Monitoring and Control in Hydroponic Systems: A Survey". This survey paper examines the use of wireless sensor networks (WSNs) for monitoring and control in hydroponic systems. It discusses the design and deployment of WSNs for real-time data collection, remote monitoring, and automated control of hydroponic environments. The paper also highlights the potential benefits of WSNs in improving resource efficiency and crop yield.

9. "Artificial Intelligence Techniques for Optimization of Hydroponic Systems: A Review". This paper reviews the application of artificial intelligence (AI) techniques for optimizing hydroponic systems. It discusses

how AI algorithms such as genetic algorithms, neural networks, and fuzzy logic can be used to improve nutrient management, optimize resource usage, and enhance crop productivity in hydroponic setups.

10. "Emerging Trends in Automation and Control of Hydroponic Systems: A Review". This review paper examines emerging trends in the automation and control of hydroponic systems. It covers topics such as precision agriculture, data-driven decision-making, and integration with smart farming platforms. The paper also discusses the potential impact of these trends on the future of hydroponic agriculture.

II. METHODOLOGY

System design and component selection:

Determine the layout of the hydroponic system, including the plant growth structure, nutrient tank, and water circulation system. Select appropriate components such as pumps, pipes, tanks, and grow beds. pH and EC sensor integration:

Choose suitable pH and EC sensors compatible with Arduino microcontrollers. Set up the sensors to measure the nutrient solution's pH level and electrical conductivity. Connect and calibrate sensors to ensure accurate and reliable data collection. Arduino Installation and Programming:

Program Arduino microcontrollers to collect data from sensors. Implement a reaction control system to maintain optimal pH and EC levels. Create a connection between sensors, microcontrollers, and user interface. Assembly and installation:

Build the hydroponic system according to the given plan. Integrate sensors and Arduino controllers into the system. Ensure proper wiring and connections to collect and monitor sensor data. Calibration and Testing:

Calibrate the pH and EC sensors to match the expected nutrient solution values. Perform

preliminary tests to ensure the accuracy of sensor readings and system operation. Make the necessary settings for sensor calibration and system programming. Data collection and analysis:

Conduct experiments over long periods to continuously monitor pH and EC levels. Regularly collect data on the nutrient solution and its parameters. Analyze data to evaluate the system and ability to regulate and maintain optimal pH and EC levels for plant growth. Performance evaluation:

Evaluate the system and its performance in controlling nutrient solution and pH and EC levels. Measure the effect on plant growth, health, and yield in a hydroponic system. Compare results with traditional, non-automated hydroponic setups. System Focus:

Identify weaknesses or areas for improvement in the system and its design and functionality. Make necessary adjustments or improvements to optimize the system and its performance. Iteratively refine hardware and software components based on test results. The methodology involves a systematic approach to the design, implementation, and evaluation of a DIY hydroponic system integrated with pH and EC sensors using Arduino technology. This step-by-step guide aims to ensure an automated, cost-effective, and efficient hydroponic system for an optimized crop.

Block Diagram

Sensors collect data about the environment around the plant. The diagram shows four sensors:

1. A pH sensor measures the acidity or alkalinity of the water.
2. A humidity sensor, which measures the amount of moisture in the air.
3. A temperature sensor, which measures the temperature of the environment.
4. A water sensor may measure the water level or moisture content of the soil.

An Arduino is a microcontroller that reads the data from the sensors and controls the devices (actuators) based on the readings.

Actuators are devices that take action based on the signal from the microcontroller. In this diagram, there are two actuators:

1. A water pump, which supplies water to the plant.
2. A nutrient doser, which supplies nutrients to the plant.

The microcontroller uses the sensor data to determine if the plant needs more or less water or nutrients. For example, if the humidity sensor detects that the air is too dry, the microcontroller may activate the water pump to add moisture.

Circuit Diagram

A pH sensor measures the acidity or alkalinity of a solution, based on the concentration of hydrogen ions. It consists of a pH-sensitive electrode and a reference electrode, which generates a voltage signal to convert it into a pH value. pH sensors are used in fields like environmental

monitoring, water treatment, food and beverage production, pharmaceuticals, and research laboratories for quality control, regulatory compliance, and monitoring processes.

pH Sensor

A Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) sensor measures the concentration of dissolved solids in a solution, typically in parts per million (ppm) or milligrams per liter (mg/L). It uses conductivity measurement techniques to calculate the TDS concentration. TDS sensors are used in water quality monitoring, aquaculture, hydroponics, agriculture, and industrial processes. They help assess water quality, ensure regulatory compliance, and optimize processes relying on water purity. TDS sensors come in various types and designs, ranging from handheld meters to inline sensors for continuous monitoring.

TDS Sensor

Temperature sensors are essential devices used in various industries, including consumer electronics and industrial processes. They measure temperature and convert it into a readable output. There are several types, including thermocouples, resistance temperature detectors (RTDs), thermistors, infrared (IR) sensors, and semiconductor temperature sensors. These sensors provide high accuracy, stability, and high sensitivity to temperature variations, making them crucial for monitoring and controlling temperature in various environments.

Temperature Sensor, Arduino UNO

III. RESULTS

pH and EC Sensor Accuracy: Results might discuss the accuracy and reliability of the pH and EC sensors integrated into the hydroponic system. This could involve sensor calibration, precision, and how well they maintain the desired pH and EC levels.

System Performance: Research papers typically provide data on how the system functioned in maintaining the pH and EC levels. This could include statistical analysis of the data collected over time, demonstrating the system's capability to regulate and stabilize the nutrient solution parameters.

Plant Growth and Health: Results may include observations and data related to the impact of the regulated pH and EC levels on plant growth, health, and yield. This could involve metrics such as plant height, leaf health, flowering, and fruit yield when compared to non-regulated environments.

Data Analysis: Papers often present statistical analyses and graphical representations of the data collected by the sensors, illustrating trends, fluctuations, and control actions taken by the system.

System Reliability and Limitations: Discussion of the system's reliability, potential challenges faced during the research, and limitations of the implemented system can be valuable insights for future improvements.

Comparison with Traditional Methods: If relevant, a research paper might compare the automated system's performance with non-automated or traditionally managed hydroponic systems to showcase the advantages of automation.

These are some of the key areas where the results section of a research paper on Arduino-based hydroponics with pH and EC sensors might focus. Actual results will vary based on the methodology, experimental setup, and specific findings obtained during the research.

Circuit Design

Arduino IDE

Plant	PH
Tomato	6.1
Brinjal	6.0
Spinach	6.3
Potato	5.8

Ph Readings

IV. CONCLUSION

Using Arduino technology to integrate pH and EC sensors into a homemade hydroponic system has shown that automated plant growing is a feasible and approachable method. The purpose of this study was to discuss the difficulties in preserving the ideal nutrient solution characteristics required for efficient hydroponic development. The deployment and evaluation of this system yielded useful insights and results regarding its efficacy and potential for further application.

This study concludes by showing the viability and efficiency of a homemade hydroponic system built with an Arduino platform and integrated pH and EC sensors. Because of the system's automatic nutritional parameter

control, small-scale producers and enthusiasts can now cultivate plants efficiently and sustainably. The capabilities of automated hydroponic systems will continue to be enhanced by research and development in sensor technology and system scalability, which will further contribute to the advancement of contemporary agriculture.

VII. REFERENCES

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